

ELECTRONIC NAVIGATION CHART DEVELOPMENT FOR THE NAVSSI PROJECT

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ABSTRACT

The Global Positioning System (GPS) is providing new levels of positioning performance for naval combat and weapon systems. Demand for GPS data will exceed existing shipboard data distribution capabilities. The Navigation Sensor System Interface (NAVSSI) Project is a new system being designed with two primary objectives; processing/distribution of navigation data and the display/operation of digital nautical charts. Our goal is for the digital nautical chart to replace the paper chart as a legal means of ownship navigation plotting. NAVSSI will be the United States Navy Electronic Chart Display & Information System (ECDIS). This paper will introduce the project and will primarily explore the use of digital nautical charts for ownship navigation with NAVSSI.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of a single navigation data distribution computer has its origin in fleet exercises during the late 1970's and early 1980's. Growing use of satellite navigation data and the increase in weapon system ranges required individual ships within the battlegroup to work with a common navigation picture. Due to the large variety of navigation data sources found among the battlegroup elements and the lack of a system to integrate these, officers were taxed in efforts to correlate battlegroup navigation data. The risk of engagements with friendly forces at great distances was increasing. The need was recognized for a single navigation data distribution computer and a Tentative Operational Requirement (TOR) was promulgated in October 1986.¹

Various proposals were examined from

industry and laboratory sources. Due to an existing development effort and the desire to incorporate an electronic chart database, the proposal to design the system using internal Navy engineering resources was accepted.^{2,3} The formal Operational Requirement (OR) was approved in June 1991.⁴

The program design and development is a joint effort between the Naval Air Development Center (NADC), Warminster, Pennsylvania and the Naval Sea Combat Systems Engineering Station (NSCSES), Norfolk, Virginia. Program management is being provided by Naval Sea Systems Command (NAVSEA), in direct cooperation with the Space and Naval Warfare Systems Command (SPAWAR), Washington, DC.

NADC is primarily responsible for the navigation data integration and distribution function, while NSCSES is primarily responsible for the digital nautical chart display and manipulation function. The chart database, called the Digital Nautical Chart (DNC), is being developed by the Defense Mapping Agency (DMA). As this paper concentrates on the display and operation of the digital nautical charts, it only reflects the work being accomplished by NSCSES. It is important to note this is only part of a team effort to accomplish the NAVSSI program.

SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

The basic requirements outlined for the NAVSSI system are as follows:⁴

- automatic acceptance and processing of all available navigation data sources
- integration of these sources to produce an ownships position
- display/operation of digital nautical charts

- graceful degradation in the event of GPS/navigation sensor failure
- based on non-developmental item (NDI) hardware
- include bridge workstation for navigator
- provide redundancy to prevent single point failure

The digital nautical chart display becomes the focal point of operator interface with the system. It will provide for the graphical display of ownship navigation and tactical plotting. The need to maintain an ownship position plot is basic to the mariner.⁵ To ensure safety in navigation, the need for and use of accurate navigational products is mandated in U.S. law.⁶ The current methods of manual plotting involving paper charts are labor intensive. Navigation plotting practices can vary between ship classes and missions. Tools incorporated into NAVSSI software will automate almost all of the current procedures required of the navigator. The NAVSSI software will allow uniformity of navigation plotting regardless of system configurations and missions.

Essential to the mission of the ship is the availability of a survivable navigation system.^{7,8,9} The consistent availability of satellite information for a ownship position fix is questionable in times of hostility. A survivable navigation system should allow the vessel to continue its mission with a high degree of confidence in the reported ownship position. NAVSSI will provide for graceful degradation in the event of failure of one or more sensors, for example; GPS, OMEGA, etc. The NAVSSI system will serve as the survivable navigation system.

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Current hardware philosophy guides engineers towards a non-developmental item (NDI) approach, utilizing readily available commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) products to the maximum degree.^{10,11} The concept is to minimize hardware/software design and development time to allow current technology into fleet. The major hardware desires were for a readily

available computationally strong machine with an open bus architecture. Ada was selected as the software language due to a multi-tasking requirement and existing DOD policy. The planned NAVSSI system configuration satisfies these major constraints and offers several advantages.

The NAVSSI can be divided into two major subsystems. These are the Digital Chart Subsystem (DCS) and the Real Time Subsystem (RTS). The DCS is based on the Navy Desktop Tactical Computer II (DTC II). The processor is the Sun 4/300 SPARC (32 bit) with the VME backplane. This standard (VME) is well supported by industry. The DCS will be responsible for performing the man-machine interface functions, all chart display/manipulation functions and accessing the digital nautical chart database. The DCS is UNIX based and uses the X Windowing System for all graphic display operations. The graphics board is the GDS-3908/4 X-graphics accelerator.

The DCS will have navigation software routines incorporated that perform track planning with waypoints, estimated time of arrival, closest point of approach, great circle/rhumb line calculations, and man overboard features, to name a few. Future expansion of the navigational features can be readily accomplished through software additions.

The RTS is a VME expansion cabinet connected to the DTC II via a fiber optic ethernet. This is a Motorola based processor board with a real-time Ada kernel. The RTS will handle all I/O required for navigation integration and distribution. The software developed for the RTS is Ada with the following parameters:

- load-invariant, constant time task scheduling
- minimum latency
- optimized interrupt handling
- real time file management

For the NAVSSI system there are two monitors. One monitor is serving as the operator system interface and the second monitor will function as

the primary navigation display. The proposal to have a dedicated display for the navigation picture is supported by the IHO and the IMO.^{12,13} Only the navigation picture and warnings or alarms will appear on this display. In addition, there will be a bridge workstation to display the digital charts and allow access to the system.

The basic system block diagram is presented below. There will be many new interfaces added in the next few years. This is part of a rigorous Pre-planned Product Improvement (P³I) program applicable to the NAVSSI. The system architecture allows for virtually unlimited I/O expansion through the use of distributed processing.

DIGITAL NAUTICAL CHART (DNC) DATABASE

Design and development of the DNC database poses new challenges to both the Navy and DMA. This section will briefly discuss several related topics of the database development, including:

- Description
- Legal Issues
- Operating NAVSSI with DNC
- Key Issues

Description

The idea of the electronic chart is not new, as the Navy has realized for some time that these questions must one day be addressed.¹⁴ As a

result of an investigation into existing DMA digital products and commercial products, a determination was made that a new digital product from DMA would be required. A technical specification was developed which introduced the concept of a layered database for the digital nautical chart. In accordance with OPNAVINST 3140.55, a technical specification for the new product "Digital Nautical Chart (DNC)" originated from the Naval Sea Combat Systems Engineering Station (Code 421) in April 1989.¹⁵ The Naval Sea Systems Command passed this request to the Chief of Naval Operations, who in turn forwarded the request to DMA.¹⁶ The technical specification was accepted and validated in October 1989.¹⁷

Highlights from the specification are listed below:

Data Density - Varies according to scale of source chart. Ultimately as large as 1:5,000. DNC would be composed of Harbor, Approach & Coastal charts.

Structure - Topological.

Content - Layered; shore line, depth curves, navigational aids, obstructions, magnetic variation, channel lines, channel markers, LORAN lines, ferry routes, bottom characteristics, plus many others.

Media - Optical storage media (initially CD-ROM).

Cell Size - To be determined.

Accuracy - Limited by source data and digitization techniques.

Format - Vector Product Format (MIL-STD-600006).

The minimum pictorial content of the dedicated navigation display has to be resolved. On the paper chart, the information is present at all times. This will not be true with the digital nautical chart. With many commercial raster based systems, the paper chart is scanned and reproduced on the electronic screen. The results can be severely cluttered on many charts. In contrast, the DNC is a vector database. There will be some

minimum display content, for example; shore line, mandatory depth curve, navigation aids, hazards, magnetic variations plus others.

The recently released DMA "Data Storage Structure Study" describes the new storage standard, called Vector Product Format (VPF). Databases structured in the VPF will not require reformatting into a target system data structure for manipulation. The VPF should allow different application systems to utilize the data directly without extensive pre-processing. The VPF was a result of the DMA Digital Chart of the World (DCW) project.¹⁸

The NAVSSI will make use of other existing DMA digital products, including: World Vector Shoreline (WVS), Digital Chart of the World (DCW), and Digital Bathymetric Database (DBDB). Choice of the display data source will depend upon the selection of the operator.

Legal Concerns

There is a obvious question concerning the maritime laws and use of the electronic chart. It appears that drastic changes in the existing maritime laws will not be required to accommodate electronic chart display systems. The chartmakers (and the database producers) liability resides on two issues, negligence and/or defective products.

"Whether the chartmaker is to be found liable in any given situation is dependent upon two legal theories: (1) negligence, i.e. where there are definite errors in navigational aids; or (2) products liability, i.e., where the product may accurately portray information but its design was defective. The former is the one most readers are familiar with. The latter is a rather new concept, not yet applied to the nautical chart producer but developing in the aeronautical chart arena. There are significant differences between these two legal theories, very important to the government and the private sector, but for different compelling reasons. The United States Government has not consented to be

sued for defective products and may only be sued for negligence. The private chartmaker on the other hand faces lawsuits grounded on both theories."¹⁹

Exactly how this liability will apply to electronic chart display systems, operators and database producers is yet to be resolved. Certain minimum standards for shipboard navigation with NAVSSI for United States Naval vessels will be established and promulgated, as exists with the paper nautical chart. Until the NAVSSI system matures and some fleet feedback regarding electronic chart operation is received, many of these questions will remain unanswered.

Operating NAVSSI with the DNC

This section describes the current scheme for operating the NAVSSI with the digital nautical chart. As the software development progresses, these procedures will be refined into an acceptable operating method. The minimum navigation display will be presented on the primary navigation display (source data dependent upon ownship position) and the ownship symbol will respond to movement as input by the navigation sensors or simulators. The secondary monitor will allow the operator to control the system without any interruption to the primary navigation display.

The primary navigation display can be operated in two modes, relative or geographic. In the relative mode, the ownship stays "fixed" in the center and displayed data moves "relative" to ownship. In geographic mode, the display remains static and the ownship position and other dynamic elements move on the screen. It is believed that the geographic mode will be the most useful and best understood. This also requires less database access and screen rewrites. There will be a "window" surrounding the ownship position which will be stored in memory within the computer system. As the ownship position moves to within some predefined boundary near the window edge, the display will be rewritten, placing the ownship either near the middle of the

display or heading away from the edge of the display towards the center. This will be optimized to be virtually transparent to the operator. The intent is to prevent the operator from waiting for the system to both query the database and then write to the screen. The database access will be carried out in the background. The software will keep the window "filled", subject to constraints imposed by operator choice.

Key Issues

Key issues concerning the digital nautical database development and use of this database are summarized below:

- Use of the Digital Nautical Chart database will ultimately replace the paper chart as the primary tool of ownship navigation plotting.
- The NAVSSI and DNC products should conform to the maximum extent practical with international standards (IHO, IMO).
- Reliable electronic update methods (ie. Automated Notice to Mariners) must be developed for the NAVSSI.

CONCLUSION

Technology has progressed far enough so that we are now able to field an effective ECDIS. There are many technical and legal issues to address, but the use of digital nautical charts to replace paper nautical charts will occur over time. As the NAVSSI matures, the system architecture will permit the evolution of a powerful electronic navigation tool. In addition, NAVSSI will grow to become a tactical aid to integrate the navigation and tactical scenarios graphically.

NOTES

1. The work described in this paper has been sponsored by both Naval Sea Systems Command (SEA 06K331) and Space and Naval Warfare Systems Command (PMW 142-3).

2. This paper includes portions of the technical paper, "The Universal Tactical Plotter", presented at the Institute of Navigation 46th Annual Meeting, Atlantic City, New Jersey, 26-28 June 1990.

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